

1 FRONT MATTER

2
3 **Title**

- 4 • Forecast skill assessment of the first continental heat-cold-health forecasting system: new
- 5 avenues for health early warning systems
- 6 • Forecast skill of heat-cold-health forecasts

7
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33
34 **Abstract**

35 Over 110,000 Europeans died as a result of the record-breaking temperatures of 2022 and
36 2023. A new generation of impact-based early warning systems, using epidemiological
37 models to transform weather forecasts into health forecasts for targeted population
38 subgroups, is an essential adaptation strategy to increase resilience against climate change.
39 Here we assessed the skill of the first continental heat-cold-health forecasting system of
40 temperature related mortality. We used state-of-the-art temperature-lag-mortality
41 epidemiological models to transform bias-corrected ensemble weather forecasts into daily
42 temperature related mortality forecasts. We found that temperature forecasts can be used to
43 issue skilful forecasts of temperature related mortality. However, the forecast skill varied
44 by season and location, and it was different for temperature and temperature related
45 mortality due to the use of epidemiological models. Overall, our study demonstrates and

46 quantifies for the first time the forecast skill horizon of heat-cold-health forecasting systems,
47 which is a necessary step towards generating trust among public health authorities and end-
48 users.

50 Teaser

51
52 Demonstration of the forecast skill of the first continental heat-cold-health forecasting
53 system to save lives.

55 MAIN TEXT

57 Introduction

58
59 Every year, over 300,000 premature deaths are related to ambient temperatures in Europe
60 (1). In the current climate, the impact of cold on human mortality surpasses that of heat by
61 a factor of ten (2), but in absence of mitigation and adaptation actions, climate change
62 projections point to the reversal of the seasonality of temperature related mortality (TRM),
63 with rapidly increasing deaths due to extreme heat (3). To reduce the negative consequences
64 of climate change on human health (4), European societies have already started to
65 implement adaptation measures (5–7). Thus, after the extreme heat in the summer of 2003
66 that caused 70,000 excess deaths in western Europe (8), several national and regional
67 meteorological and public health agencies started to design and implement heat early
68 warning systems.

69 However, the death toll arising from the record-breaking temperatures in 2022 and 2023,
70 with over 110,000 heat related deaths in the continent(1, 9, 10), emphasised again the need
71 to further strengthen existing emergency and resilience plans, including the development of
72 a new generation of heat-cold-health early warning systems. Existing operational systems
73 generally rely only on physical data from operational weather forecasts to activate public
74 health actions, and therefore they neither account for the real impacts on the exposed
75 populations nor for the inequalities in vulnerability to heat and cold across different
76 population subgroups, which is key to protect vulnerable populations (11). Current
77 protocols, methodologies and warning issuing criteria largely vary from one country to
78 another, but the vast majority of them are actually entirely based on regional thresholds of
79 temperature, and in a few cases, on other climate variables (e.g. humidity) (12), combined
80 indices (e.g. apparent temperature) (12) or even thermo-physiological parameters (13).

81 Determining the forecast skill horizon of any operational forecasting system is key to issue
82 early warnings that generate trust among end-users. Over the last decades, numerical
83 weather prediction (14) has shifted from a deterministic (single numerical integration) to a
84 probabilistic approach (ensembles of numerical integrations with perturbed initial
85 conditions). This change has allowed a substantial improvement of forecast skill horizons
86 beyond the previously thought 2-week limit arising from the chaotic nature of the
87 atmosphere (15, 16). To issue early warnings directly targeting the impacts of temperatures
88 on human health, epidemiological models need to be used to transform weather forecasts
89 into forecast of health-related variables, e.g. mortality or morbidity (17–19). Importantly, it
90 yet remains to be explored if this transformation preserves the skill horizon found in weather
91 forecasting systems for physical variables such as temperature. This skill assessment of
92 health-related forecasts requires the transdisciplinary integration of weather forecasts and

93 techniques with health datasets and epidemiological models to develop and evaluate health
94 early warning systems directly targeting impact-based health variables (20).

95
96 The overarching goal of the present study is to analyse and explain the differences in the
97 forecast skill of temperature and TRM forecasts in Europe, both focusing on winter and
98 summer months, as a necessary step towards the release of Forecaster.Health
99 (<https://forecaster.health/>), the first operational, open-access, continental heat-cold-health
100 early warning system (21, 22).

101 Results

102
103 Figure 1a shows the cumulative exposure-response association accumulated over the range
104 of lags in southern, western and central Europe, and Figure S1 the association for the
105 ensemble of 147 European regions here analysed (see Methods). The relative risk (RR)
106 of death is found to monotonically increase for temperatures above and below the minimum
107 mortality temperature (MMT), which in the ensemble of regions analysed, is always found
108 between percentiles 78 and 93 of the respective distribution of daily regional temperatures
109 (Figure S2). The cold part of the association therefore covers a wider range of temperatures,
110 although the increase in the RR per 1°C is nonlinear and much steeper in the warm tail.
111 Figures 1b,c additionally depict the lag-response association at the 1st and 99th temperature
112 percentiles, respectively, showing how the RR at extreme cold and warm temperatures is
113 differently distributed along the range of lags. Thus, the risk of death for warm temperatures
114 is immediate, acute and generally does not last for more than five days, while the effect of
115 cold temperatures starts 1 or 2 days later, and it is distributed along a wider range of lags of
116 a few weeks. Figures 1d-f depict the regional differences in the MMT and the RR at the 1st
117 and 99th temperature percentiles, respectively. The regional MMTs are latitudinally
118 distributed, i.e. the warmer is the climate of a region the warmer is its optimum temperature,
119 showing the effect of long-term adaptation to climatological conditions (5, 23) (Figure 1d).
120 Moreover, the risk of death is relatively homogenous for cold temperatures (Figure 1e),
121 while a latitudinal pattern emerges for heat with higher RR values in southern Europe
122 (Figure 1f).
123
124

125 We used the regional epidemiological associations in Figure S1 to transform the daily
126 timeseries of observed and forecast temperatures into timeseries of observed and forecast
127 TRM values at lead times of up to 15 days. Figure 2 shows the associations and the square
128 of the Pearson correlations (R^2) between daily observations and ensemble mean forecasts
129 aggregated over the ensemble of regions at different lead times. Correlations are found to
130 monotonically decay as a function of the forecast lead time, and in all cases, they are higher
131 in winter than in summer. The difference in correlation between winter and summer is found
132 to increase with the lead time, and to be generally higher for TRM. The rather small
133 correlation differences between winter and summer temperatures at short lead times are
134 found to be amplified by the decay of the forecast skill at larger lead times (cf. R^2 values in
135 panels a-c), as well as by the added complexity and diversity of the regional epidemiological
136 associations transforming temperatures into TRM values (cf. a-c with d-f).
137

138 In subsequent figures, we explore how these regional epidemiological transformations
139 differently modify the forecast skill horizon, so that the range of lead times with skilful
140 TRM forecasts is to a large extent dependent on the season and location. We evaluated the
141 forecast skill of temperature and TRM forecasts by computing the ranked probability skill
142 score (RPSS) (see Methods), a probabilistic measure accounting for the ensemble of

143 forecast members and its uncertainty. Figure 3 shows the RPSS of temperature and TRM
144 forecasts aggregated for the ensemble of regions as a function of the forecast lead time, and
145 Figure S3 the corresponding values for each individual region. As previously seen in the
146 correlations of Figure 2, the forecast skill monotonically decays with the lead time, being
147 generally higher in winter than in summer, and higher for temperature than for TRM. We
148 note that these two basic characteristics of the forecast skill are generally found in most of
149 the regions (Figure S3). We found that the forecast skill horizon, here defined as the lead
150 time at which the RPSS is equal to 0.2, is almost the same for temperature and TRM in
151 winter (10.7 and 10.5 days respectively), while in summer it is clearly higher for
152 temperature (9.5 days) than for TRM (8.3 days). We note, however, that the RPSS in winter
153 is greater than zero at least at lead time 15 days both for temperature and TRM, and in
154 summer beyond 14 days for temperature and around 11.5 days for TRM.
155

156 Figure 4 explores the spatial heterogeneity of the forecast skill horizon, as well as the loss
157 of forecast skill due to the regional epidemiological transformations, here quantified as the
158 difference in the forecast skill horizon of temperature minus that of TRM. Again, the
159 forecast skill horizon is found to be generally higher in winter than in summer, and for
160 temperature than for TRM. In winter, the forecast skill horizon of temperature is between 2
161 and 3 days higher in north-eastern Europe than in southern and western Europe (Figure 4a),
162 possibly due to the more persistent, and thus predictable, winter conditions of the
163 continental climate, characterised by the Eurasian snow cover (24) or through the direct
164 effect of the polar vortex (25, 26). Similar values and spatial distribution are found for TRM
165 in winter (Figure 4b), with generally no loss of forecast skill due to the regional
166 epidemiological transformations (i.e. regional forecast skill horizon differences generally
167 between -0.2 and +0.8 days, see Figure 4c). Instead, in summer, forecast skill horizon values
168 are found to be spatially homogeneous for temperature, but with some changes in the case
169 of TRM (Figures 4d,e). Moreover, there is a clear loss of forecast skill due to the regional
170 epidemiological transformations in summer, with a difference of up to 2 days in several
171 regions in western and central Europe (Figure 4f). Importantly, the loss of forecast skill is
172 smaller in the Mediterranean basin, which is the region with the highest vulnerability to heat
173 (cf. Figures 1f and 4f).
174

175 Finally, Figure 5 shows how the regional loss of forecast skill is explained by the shape of
176 the regional epidemiological associations. On the one hand, in summer, we found a clear
177 association between the loss of forecast skill and the MMT percentile (MMTP, Figure 5b),
178 i.e. the percentile of the daily temperature distribution corresponding to the MMT. The
179 regional MMTPs are always found between percentiles 78 and 93 (Figure S2), that is, at
180 temperatures that are generally observed within the summer season. This means that
181 temperatures are colder than the MMT in a fraction of summer days, and consequently, in
182 these days, the TRM increases with decreasing (not increasing) temperatures below the
183 MMT (see the asymmetric V-shaped curves in Figure 1a). In other words, the colder is a
184 regional MMTP, the more infrequent is the occurrence of regional temperatures colder than
185 the MMT in summer, and therefore, the stronger and more monotonically increasing is the
186 epidemiological association transforming the summer temperatures into TRM values, and
187 consequently, the smaller is the amplification of errors in the temperature forecasts by the
188 epidemiological transformations. On the other hand, in winter, the association between the
189 regional MMTP and the regional loss of forecast skill is weak (Figure 5a). This is possibly
190 explained by the lower spatial heterogeneity in the loss of forecast skill (Figure 4c), but also
191 by the asymmetric V-shaped curve of the epidemiological associations (Figure 1a), with the
192 MMT never observed in winter.

243 weather forecast systems in these areas. Even with these possible improvements, our study
244 showed that the loss of forecast skill (of the order of 0-2 days) is found to be small compared
245 to the overall forecast skill horizon of weather forecasts (8-11 days), which implies that the
246 forecast skill of operational health early warning systems is to a very large extent influenced
247 by the forecast skill of the temperature forecasts, and to a much lesser extent by the
248 epidemiological models. In other words, our results indicate that any further improvement
249 in weather (and subseasonal-to-seasonal climate) forecasting would automatically turn into
250 an increase in the forecast skill horizon of operational health early warning systems.

251
252 More importantly, we demonstrated that the skill assessment of impact-based health early
253 warning systems should account for both the forecast skill of the weather variables (e.g.
254 temperature) and the corresponding epidemiological association with the health variable
255 (e.g. mortality), both being crucial to determine when derived action measures are activated.
256 This result emphasises the pressing need to develop a new interdisciplinary field at the
257 interplay between research and innovation, which combines weather and climate forecasting
258 with epidemiology and social sciences (21, 31), as recently done with the release of the first
259 continental heat-cold-health forecasting system of temperature related mortality
260 (<https://forecaster.health/>) (22). This emerging domain of science would transform the
261 existing forecast skill of the physical variables of the Earth system into a range of early
262 warning systems of health indicators directly targeting vulnerable populations at a range of
263 spatiotemporal scales. The forecast skill of these innovative tools would be assessed, as we
264 here did, by comparing the forecast skill horizon of weather and climate forecasts with that
265 of impact-based health forecasts. The World Health Organization highlights the importance
266 of providing effective climate services and health early warning systems for saving lives in
267 vulnerable communities around the world (11). Our methodological framework could be
268 generally applied to any social determinant of health (early warning systems by sex, age,
269 socioeconomic level or comorbidities), variable (mortality, morbidity and occupational
270 health) or lead time (from days to months) as long as health data is available to calibrate
271 epidemiological models specifically targeting these groups and variables. The development
272 of these innovative tools, supported by a rigorous assessment of their forecast skill, as we
273 demonstrated here, would generate trust among public health authorities and end-users, and
274 at the same time, increase resilience and strengthen our early adaptation response to climate
275 change.

276 **Materials and Methods**

277 **Mortality data**

278 We used a spatiotemporally-homogeneous daily regional mortality database for the period
279 1998-2012 (2). The dataset consisted of $N = 58,784,430$ counts of deaths from 147
280 contiguous NUTS (Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics, version of 2013 (32))
281 regions in 16 European countries, representing their entire urban and rural population of
282 420 million people. These countries are Austria (9 NUTS2 regions), Belgium (11 NUTS2),
283 Switzerland (7 NUTS2), Czechia (8 NUTS2), Germany (16 NUTS1), Denmark (1 NUTS1),
284 Spain (16 NUTS2), France (22 NUTS2), Croatia (2 NUTS2), Italy (21 NUTS2),
285 Luxembourg (1 NUTS3), Netherlands (1 NUTS0), Poland (16 NUTS2), Portugal (5
286 NUTS2), Slovenia (1 NUTS1) and United Kingdom (10 NUTS1, regions in England and
287 Wales only). Further details are provided in previously published studies (23, 33, 34).
288
289
290

291 **Temperature data**

We obtained gridded ($0.1^\circ \times 0.1^\circ$) daily mean 2-meter temperatures from E-OBS (version 29.0) (35) for the period 1998-2020, which we here consider as a proxy for observations. We also obtained gridded (interpolated to $0.4^\circ \times 0.4^\circ$) 6-hourly forecasts of 2-meter temperature for the period 2009-2020 from the ECMWF ensemble prediction system (Atmospheric model Ensemble 15-day forecast, Set III – ENS) (36) archived in the TIGGE database (37–39). We retrieved the $M = 50$ perturbed ensemble members, initialised at 00 UTC across forecast lead times +6h, +12h, +18h, ..., +360h, covering lead times from 1 to 15 days. We derived the regional daily temperatures by computing the temperature average of grid-cell data within the regional boundaries of each of the 147 regions analysed. For the forecasts, after deriving the regional 6-hourly forecasts first, we averaged them to obtain the daily mean temperature forecast for lead times 1 (average of +6h, +12h, +18h and +24h lead times) to 15 days (average of +342h, +348h, +354h and +360h lead times).

Bias correction of temperature forecasts

We post-processed the ensemble of temperature forecasts to bias-correct them, so that the temperature forecasts are aligned with the temperature observations used in the epidemiological models. By doing so, we also improved the skill of the temperature and temperature related mortality (TRM) forecasts (40). We applied a state-of-the-art, widely-used in operational forecasting, bias-correction method considering the most recent $N = 30$ pairs of observations and forecasts with respect to each forecast start date (BC-30) (29). Thus, for any given region r , observation date or forecast start date s , and forecast lead time l (taking values from 1 to 15 days), we calculated the correction c of the ensemble member forecasts as:

$$c(r, s, l) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N (o(r, s - n) - f_{ave}(r, s - n - l + 1, l)),$$

where $o(r, s - n)$ and $f_{ave}(r, s - n - l + 1, l)$ are the pairs of temperature observations and ensemble mean forecasts for all cases in the training dataset, respectively. We then added this correction individually to each of the $M = 50$ ensemble members to obtain the ensemble of bias-corrected temperature forecasts.

Epidemiological model

We used a time-series quasi-Poisson regression model in combination with a distributed lag non-linear model in each region to derive estimates of region-specific temperature-lag-mortality risks (41). The equation is as follows

$$\log(E(mort)) = intercept + S(time, 8 \text{ df per year}) + dow + cb$$

where $mort$ denotes the daily time series of mortality counts; E corresponds to its expected value; S is a natural cubic spline of time with 8 degrees of freedom per year to adjust for the seasonal and long-term trends; dow corresponds to a categorical variable to control for the day of the week; and cb is the cross-basis function produced by the distributed lag non-linear model combining the exposure-response and lag-response associations (41). The exposure-response association was modelled with a natural cubic spline, with three internal knots placed at the 10th, 75th and 90th percentiles of the observed distribution of daily regional temperatures during 1998-2012. The lag-response association was modelled with a natural cubic spline, with three internal knots placed at equally-spaced intervals in the log scale, with a maximum lag of 21 days, and an intercept. We then performed a multivariate

340 multilevel meta-analysis, modelling dependencies of regions within countries through
 341 structured random effects (42). The fitted meta-analytical model was used to derive the best
 342 linear unbiased predictions of the cumulative temperature-mortality associations in each
 343 region, from which we estimated the regional minimum mortality temperature (MMT),
 344 which was used as the baseline temperature of the regional association. All these modelling
 345 choices have been widely tested and used in the epidemiological literature (2, 43).

347 **Temperature related mortality (TRM)**

348 The daily regional timeseries representing the fraction of deaths attributable to non-optimal
 349 temperatures (44), here referred to as temperature related mortality (TRM), was calculated
 350 as

$$352 \text{TRM}(d) = \frac{RR(T(d)) - 1}{RR(T(d))}$$

353 where d represents a given date, and $RR(T(d))$ is the relative risk at temperature $T(d)$,
 354 compared to the baseline MMT, as defined by the respective regional cumulative
 355 temperature-mortality association. We transformed every daily regional timeseries of
 356 temperature (i) observations and (ii) bias-corrected ensemble member forecasts into daily
 357 regional timeseries of TRM (i) estimations and (ii) ensemble member forecasts. For the sake
 358 of simplicity, we here refer to the TRM estimations as *TRM observations* throughout the
 359 manuscript, although we acknowledge the fact that TRM is a variable that cannot be directly
 360 observed or measured.

363 **Temperature and TRM forecast skill**

364 We quantified the forecast skill by calculating a modified version of the ranked probability
 365 score (RPS) (45). This probabilistic assessment of the forecast skill considers forecast
 366 uncertainty, in contrast to deterministic approaches (40). We applied the exact same
 367 approach separately to the ensemble of temperature and the ensemble of TRM forecasts.

369 First, both for temperature and TRM, we calculated the RPS for any given region r ,
 370 observation date or forecast start date s , and forecast lead time l (from 1 to 15 days) as

$$372 \text{RPS}(r, s, l) = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{m=1}^M |o(r, s) - f_m(r, s - l + 1, l)|,$$

373 where $o(r, s)$ and $f_m(r, s - l + 1, l)$ are the pairs of observation and forecast ensemble
 374 member m . Then, we averaged the RPS across all winter (December-February) or summer
 375 (June-August) days during the period 2009-2020, to obtain the mean RPS in each region
 376 and forecast lead time, here represented as $\overline{\text{RPS}}(r, l)$.

379 We calculated the skill of a reference temperature or TRM forecast consisting of the
 380 climatology of the observations in the 23-year reference period 1998-2020. By construction,
 381 these climatological forecasts provide no valuable forecast information, and are thus used
 382 as a reference baseline to $\overline{\text{RPS}}(r, l)$. The RPS for the climatological forecasts, here
 383 represented as RPS_{CL} , was calculated as

$$\text{RPS}_{\text{CL}}(r, d) = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K |o(r, d'_k) - o(r, d)|,$$

where $o(r, d)$ are the observations for any given region r and date d , and d'_k refers to the set of days on the same calendar day than d within the 23-year reference period 1998-2020 ($K = 23$). Leap days were not only compared to other leap days, but also to all the February 28ths and March 1sts in other years. In the same way, we calculated the mean skill of the climatological forecasts in each region for the winter and summer seasons, *i. e.* $\overline{\text{RPS}}_{\text{CL}}(r)$.

The resulting indicator we used for evaluating the forecast skill for each region r and forecast lead time l is the ranked probability skill score (RPSS) (46), defined as follows:

$$\text{RPSS}(r, l) = 1 - \frac{\overline{\text{RPS}}(r, l)}{\overline{\text{RPS}}_{\text{CL}}(r)}.$$

High RPSS values represent high forecast skill, with a maximum value of 1 when forecast errors are infinitely smaller than the corresponding climatological forecasts. Positive RPSS values indicate forecast errors smaller than those of a purely climatological forecast, and negative RPSS values indicate that forecasts provide no valuable forecast skill. Nonetheless, we here used a stricter threshold to define the forecast skill horizon as the lead time (in days) with a regional RPSS value of 0.2 (15, 47). Finally, we defined the regional loss of forecast skill due to the epidemiological transformations as the difference of the regional forecast skill horizon of temperature minus the regional forecast skill horizon of TRM.

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587

588 **Data and materials availability:**

589 Temperature data used underlying this article can be accessed by the corresponding
590 institutions (<https://www.ecmwf.int/en/forecasts/datasets/set-iii>;
591 <https://www.ecad.eu/download/ensembles/download.php>). Daily deaths count data were
592 provided by the corresponding national statistical offices. The “dlnm” R package is
593 available on CRAN (<http://cran.r-project.org/>) and codes on examples of applications of the
594 distributed lag nonlinear models are available at [http://www.ag-myresearch.com/r-](http://www.ag-myresearch.com/r-code.html)
595 [code.html](http://www.ag-myresearch.com/r-code.html). All data needed to evaluate the conclusions in the paper are present in the paper
596 and/or Supplementary Materials.
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598

599 **Figures and Tables**
600

601 **Fig. 1. Observed temperature-mortality associations (1998-2012).** Panels a-c show the
602 relative risk (unitless) of death accumulated over the range of lags (a), and for
603 percentiles 1 (b) and 99 (c) of the daily temperature distribution. These relative risks
604 were predicted for central (Austria, Switzerland, Czechia, Germany, Denmark,
605 Croatia, Poland and Slovenia; in black), southern (Spain, Italy and Portugal; in red)
606 and western (Belgium, France, Luxembourg, Netherlands and England and Wales;
607 in blue) Europe. Panel d depicts the regional minimum mortality temperature (°C),
608 and panels e-f the regional relative risk (unitless) of death for percentiles 1 (e) and
609 99 (f) of the daily temperature distribution.
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Fig. 2. Association between daily temperature (a-c, in °C) or temperature related mortality -TRM- (d-f, in %) observations and forecasts (2009-2020). Each point represents a couple of daily winter (December to February, in blue) or summer (June to August, in red) observed and ensemble mean forecast values aggregated over the ensemble of European regions at lead times of 1 (a,d), 5 (b,e) and 9 (c,f) days. The square of the Pearson correlation (R^2) is shown in the top left corner (all correlations are $p < 0.001$).

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Fig. 3. Decay of the forecast skill as a function of the forecast lead time (2009-2020). The forecast skill of winter (December to February, a) and summer (June to August,

624 b) temperature (red) and temperature related mortality (TRM) forecasts (blue) is
625 measured with the ranked probability skill score (RPSS). The forecast skill horizon
626 is defined as the lead time at which the RPSS is equal to 0.2.
627

628 **Fig. 4. Forecast skill horizon and loss of forecast skill due to the epidemiological**
629 **transformations (2008-2020).** The forecast skill horizon is defined as the lead time
630 at which ranked probability skill score is equal to 0.2, and the loss of forecast skill
631 due to the regional epidemiological transformations as the difference in the forecast
632 skill horizon of temperature and temperature related mortality (TRM). The regional
633 forecast skill horizon is shown for winter (December to February, a-b) and summer
634 (June to August, d-e) temperature (a,d) and TRM forecasts (b,e). Panels c and f
635 depict the loss of forecast skill in winter and summer, respectively.
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 639 **Fig. 5. Factors of the epidemiological associations explaining the regional differences**
 640 **in loss of forecast skill.** The loss of forecast skill due to the regional epidemiological
 641 transformations is defined as the difference in the forecast skill horizon of
 642 temperature and TRM. Panel a show the relationship between the percentile of the
 643 minimum mortality temperature and the loss of forecast skill in winter, and panel b
 644 the same association in summer.

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 646 **Supplementary Materials**

647 Available in [advances_supplementary_materials_template_2022.pdf](#)
 648